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PROCEEDINGS

SANDUSKY RIVER BASIN SYMPOSIUM

MAY 2 - 3, 1975

TIFFIN, OHIO

Co-sponsors: Heidelberg College
Bowling Green State University

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SANDUSKY RIVER BASIN SYMPOSIUM

MAY 2-3, 1975

Tiffin, Ohio

SPONSORED BY

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Tiffin, Ohio 44883

BOWLING GREEN STATE UNIVERSITY
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PREFACE

The Sandusky River Basin Symposium, held at Heidelberg College in Tiffin, Ohio and jointly sponsored by Heidelberg and Bowling Green State University, brought together more than 150 persons engaged in environmental research, monitoring, and management, both in the Sandusky Basin and from surrounding areas. The program scope and the purpose of the symposium indicated:

A considerable amount of ecological research and monitoring activity is taking place within the Sandusky River and Bay areas. The research ranges from studies of the geology, hydrology, and soils of the basin and bay to measurements of the biological and chemical characteristics of the river and bay. In this conference, the individuals who are involved in the entire scope of the above research efforts, as well as those involved with water quality management within the basin, will present their research results and current management practices.

The purpose of this conference is to provide an opportunity for the scientists engaged in ecological research and those engaged in management to exchange detailed information that will aid both in future work. The conference should also provide useful information to individuals working in other river basin studies and anyone interested in the relationships between ecosystem research and river basin management.

The symposium was successful in attaining many of these objectives, and the diversity and detail of environment-related studies underway in the Sandusky Basin and Bay areas was impressive. The historical perspectives of this region, as brought forth in papers by Trautman, Forsyth, and Stuckey, created a useful foundation. The keynote address by Cummins, extending stream ecosystem theory to larger rivers, had significant impact on both ecosystem concepts and management applications. The contributions of personnel in governmental agencies provided an overview of programs within which environmental planning and management take place.

The program of the symposium has been reproduced in the table of contents. The proceedings differ from the symposium in that the many excellent color slides, which potentiated the presentations, necessarily have been replaced by tabular data. Both these quantitative and qualitative presentations will aid future studies in this basin and other areas.

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ABSTRACT

DISTRIBUTION OF NON-POINT SOURCES OF PHOSPHOROUS AND SEDIMENT IN
THE SANDUSKY RIVER BASIN

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The average annual transport of soluble orthophosphorus, total phosphorous and suspended solids has been calculated at each of five U.S. Geological Survey stream gages in the Sandusky Basin. Calculations were based on numerous instantaneous loading measurements taken between July, 1969 and November, 1974. For each station, weighted mean concentrations were obtained by dividing total flow volume during the periods of observation. Average annual transport was then calculated by multiplying weighted mean concentrations by average annual flows.

The 4 values following each stream gage listed below represent consecutively the annual transport of total phosphorous (as P) in short tons, the phosphorous runoff coefficient in lbs/sq mi/yr. The values for each stream gage were: Tymochtee - 88,769, 48,000 and 210; Bucyrus - 51, 1150, 14,000 and 157; Upper Sandusky - 148, 993, 58, 300 and 196; Mexico - 314, 811, 199,000 and 257; and Tiffin - 509, 813, 271,000 and 217.

The drainage areas above each of the five stream gages define five subbasins. For each subbasin, annual point source inputs of phosphorous were determined and, along with phosphorous inputs from upstream subbasins, subtracted from the annual output from the subbasin. This provided an estimate of non-source runoff coefficients in lbs of total phosphorous/acre/yr were: Tymochtee, 1.20; Bucyrus, 0.22; Upper Sandusky, 1.25; Mexico, 0.88; and Tiffin, 0.93. The annual yield of total phosphorous from non-point sources in the basin was 390 tons of 77% of the total annual yield. For the entire 1251 sq mi basin, the average non-point source phosphorous runoff coefficient was 0.98 lbs/acre/yr, an extremely high value in comparison with other values in the literature. Most of this phosphorous is associated with clay particles which dominate the suspended solids loaded in the stream.

THE DISTRIBUTION OF NON-POINT SOURCES OF PHOSPHORUS AND SEDIMENT
IN THE SANDUSKY RIVER BASIN

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Much effort is currently directed toward reducing phosphorus loading into Lake Erie from its tributary streams. This effort is concentrated on the phosphorus originating at municipal sewage treatment plants because the appropriate technology exists and because municipal sewage apparently is the major source of phosphorus enrichment in Lake Erie (U.S. Department of Interior 1968).

As more detailed studies of nutrient loading from tributaries into Lake Erie are being completed, it is becoming evident that large amounts of phosphorus originating from general land use activities are also being transported into the lake. We have shown that a minimum of 75% of the total phosphorus delivered to Lake Erie from the Sandusky Basin must originate from rural non-point sources (Baker and Kramer, 1973). Furthermore, the observed runoff coefficient for total phosphorus from rural non-point sources (1.03 kg/ha/yr) was 2.4 times larger than the value used to estimate phosphorus yields from rural land in North Central Ohio in early phosphorus balance calculations for Lake Erie.

This report contains a more detailed study of the sources of phosphorus and sediments within the Sandusky River Basin. Phosphorus and sediment balances for five subbasins are developed. These data reflect the status of phosphorus sources before the onset of phosphorus removal measures at the municipal sewage treatment plants in the basin. Studies currently in progress are directly evaluating the effects of municipal phosphorus removal on the transport of phosphorus from this river basin into Lake Erie and on the water quality of the stream.

METHODS

Model for calculating non-point source yields

We have calculated non-point source yields of phosphorus and sediments from individual subbasins of the Sandusky River Basin using the model illustrated in Figure 1. Materials in the stream system within any subbasin can originate from: (1) streams flowing into the subbasin, i.e. upstream inputs; (2) point source inputs within the subbasin; or (3) non-point source inputs within the subbasin. The material yield from any subbasin consists solely of the stream output. By assuming that all of the material entering the subbasin from upstream inputs and point source inputs is transported through the subbasin, we can calculate the *minimum yield* from non-point sources by subtracting the upstream inputs and the point source inputs from the total output. This calculation represents the *minimum yield* from non-point sources because, if either upstream or point source inputs are permanently lost from the flowing river system within the subbasin, a larger portion of the total stream output would have to be accounted for by non-point sources. Such losses could occur by deposition on flood plains or behind dams or by biological pathways. The model assumes that on an annual basis, there is no net accumulation of phosphorus or sediments in the river system.

The assumptions of the model can be explained in terms of delivery ratios. Delivery ratio is normally defined as the ratio of the sediment yield from a drainage area to the gross erosion rate within that drainage area, expressed as a percentage (Gottschalk, 1964). It is convenient to extend this concept to include phosphorus from both non-point and point sources and also to apply the general concept of output-to-input ratio to characterize

Figure 1 Model for the calculation of non-point source yields of materials from subbasins of the Sandusky River Basin.

transport through sections of the stream. For upstream inputs of both sediment and phosphorus, delivery ratios through the subbasins are assumed to be 100%. Likewise the delivery ratio of phosphorus from point sources is assumed to be 100%. No assumptions are made for the delivery ratio of materials originating from non-point sources. Consequently, the gross erosion rate within a subbasin cannot be calculated from the sediment yield of that subbasin. Also non-point source "inputs" of phosphorus cannot be calculated from the non-point source yield of phosphorus.

In applying the above model, accurate measurements of material transport in the river on the input and output sides of each subbasin are required. Existing U.S. Geological Survey Stream Gages provide locations where the necessary stream flow data are available for calculations of material transport. The locations of these stream gages in the basin determine the size and shape of the subbasins. In the Sandusky River Basin, five continuously recording stream gages are present. The locations of these stream gages and the resulting subbasins which they delineate are shown in Figure 2. The area, population, and physical characteristics of each subbasin are shown in Table 1.

Sample collection

The data presented in this report were obtained between January 1969 and December 1974. Periods of high, medium and low flows during all seasons of the year are included.

Before March 1974, all samples were collected using plastic buckets lowered from bridges near the stream gage sites. Stream flow at each of the sites is turbulent, especially during periods of high flow. Particle size analysis of samples from the Sandusky River indicates that more than 96% of the sediment is in the clay and silt fractions, having fall diameters less

Figure 2 Map of the Sandusky River Basin showing the names, shapes and locations of the individual subbasins. The identification numbers of the U.S. Geological Survey stream gages which comprise the output/input stations for each basin are also shown.

Table 1: Area, Population and Physical Features of Subbasins of the Sandusky River Basin*

Subbasin	Subbasin Area ₂ km ²	Population Total ₂ #/km ²	Density Rural ₂ #/km ²	General Description
Tymochtee	593	11.0	11.0	Bedrock-- Silurean Age dolomite and limestone; topography -- relatively flat till plain traversed by terminal moraines; soils -- high lime glacial till.
Bucyrus	230	112.4	29.5	Bedrock -- Mississippian Age shales and sandstones; topography -- relatively flat till plains traversed by terminal moraines; soils -- high lime glacial till.
Upper Sandusky	542	26.4	16.0	Bedrock -- Devonian and Silurean Age dolomite and limestone; topography -- relatively flat till plains traversed by terminal moraines; soils -- both high and low lime glacial tills.
Mexico	640	19.7	14.1	Bedrock -- Devonian and Silurean Age dolomite and limestone; topography -- relatively flat till plains traversed by terminal moraines; soils -- mostly high lime glacial tills.
Tiffin	1235	38.0	19.0	Bedrock -- Devonian and Silurean Age dolomite and limestone; topography -- mostly flat to gently rolling lake plains; soils-- dark colored, poorly drained clay soils in northern part, high lime glacial till in southern part.

* Metric-English Conversion:

1 square kilometer = 0.386 square miles

than 0.031 mm (Ohio Department of Natural Resources, 1966; U.S. Department of Interior, 1974). Given the turbulence and the fine particle size, grab samples should yield essentially the same results as samples obtained with depth-integrating techniques.

In order to obtain more detailed information on changing phosphorus and sediment concentrations during runoff events, three automatic sequential samplers were put into operation in March 1974. These samplers were located at the gage stations where continuous monitors for dissolved oxygen, temperature, pH and conductivity are in operation (Upper Sandusky, Tymochtee and Mexico). The pumps of the automatic samplers withdrew water from the probe tanks of the continuous monitors. High volume pumps provide a continuous flow of river water through the probe tanks. Sediment and phosphorus analyses on samples collected from the probe tanks agreed very closely with similar analyses on grab samples from the stream. The automatic samplers were set to collect discrete samples at 6 to 8 hour intervals. The samplers contained enough bottles for one week of sampling.

With the exception of samples obtained by the automatic samplers, almost all of the samples were analyzed within 24 hours of the time of collection. In most cases, samples were collected in the morning and analyzed the same afternoon. Consequently, no preservation techniques were employed. Preservatives were not used in bottles within the automatic samplers. In tests of samples obtained during winter and spring runoff events, dissolved orthophosphate showed little change during one week of storage within the sampler. Mercuric chloride was tested as a preservative for these samples. It provided no advantage over unpreserved samples and its use was discontinued.

Analytical methods

Both total phosphorus (Storet #0065) and dissolved orthophosphate (Storet #00671) were measured by the single reagent method as outlined in *Methods for Analysis of Water and Wastes* (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1971). Before 1974, all of the colorimetry was done using a Klett-Summerson colorimeter. Since that date, a Technicon Autoanalyzer II System has been used. For total phosphorus, samples with high suspended sediments were filtered through glass-fiber filters after the persulfate digestion. The digestion was done in an autoclave and the samples were filtered while still hot.

Suspended sediments (Storet #00530) were also done according to the methods outlined in the above manual. A well-mixed sample was filtered through a preweighed glass-fiber filter (Reeve Angel 934AH) and the residue retained on the filter was dried to a constant weight at 103-105 degrees C.

Flow measurements

At the time of sample collection, the river stage was either measured with a wire weight gage or read from the tape punch equipment in the gage house. The U.S. Geological Survey provided a rating table for each station for converting river stages into flows. Where the automatic samplers were used, the river stages at the time of sample collection were obtained from printouts of hourly gage height data supplied by the U.S. Geological Survey.

RESULTS

Figure 3 illustrates the typical changes in sediment and phosphorus concentrations which occur during runoff events. These samples were collected

Figure 3 Hydrographs, sediment graphs and chemigraphs for two runoff events at the Tymochee stream gage occurring between March 28 and April 10, 1974. Samples were collected at 6 hour intervals. The time base is in units of 2 hour increments beginning at the starting time of 400 hours March 28, 1974.

at six-hour intervals during two runoff events at the Tymochtee stream gage in March and April 1974. The concentrations of both suspended sediments and total phosphorus increased rapidly during the initial phases of the runoff events. Concentrations of both of these started to decrease before the peak flows were reached. The "fine structure" of the total phosphorus and suspended solids curves are very similar. Although much lower in absolute value, the concentrations of dissolved orthophosphorus at this station also increased during the runoff events.

To estimate the mean annual transport at each gage station, using data of the type illustrated in Figure 3, we calculated weighted mean concentrations of total phosphorus, soluble phosphorus and suspended solids. The weighted mean concentrations were obtained by dividing the observed total loading by the observed total flow (table 2). Total loadings and total flows were calculated using the mid-interval technique, as employed by the U.S. Geological Survey at their sediment-transport stations (Porterfield, 1972.) For example, if samples were collected at six-hour intervals, the instantaneous flux rate and flow rate at the time of sample collection are assumed to characterize the stream conditions for the three hours before and after the sample collection. The total transport during the six-hour period was calculated and summed with similar calculations for all of the other samples collected at that stream gage. This method of calculating weighted mean concentrations reduces the bias which could be introduced when samples are collected at six-hour intervals during runoff events but at 24-hour intervals during lower flows.

Table 2: Data Base for Calculations of Weighted Mean Concentrations of Orthophosphorus (O.P.), Total Phosphorus (T.P.) and Suspended Sediments (S.S.) at U.S. Geological Survey Stream Gages in the Sandusky River Basin *

Station	Parameter	Number of Measurements	Mean Flow During Sampling m ³ /s	Observed Total Loading metric tons	Observed Total Flow 10 ³ m ³	Weighted Mean Concentration mg/l
Tymochtee	O.P.	563	4.61	10.56	1.48	0.071
	T.P.	593	5.46	92.57	1.86	0.498
	S.S.	533	5.68	45,550	1.68	271
Bucyrus	O.P.	309	2.56	8.35	0.36	0.230
	T.P.	303	2.42	18.81	0.33	0.563
	S.S.	316	2.71	6,766	0.39	173
Upper Sandusky	O.P.	570	7.46	37.0	2.66	0.139
	T.P.	554	8.68	180.9	3.12	0.580
	S.S.	536	9.40	88,450	3.01	294.0
Mexico	O.P.	336	20.4	59.2	6.08	0.098
	T.P.	360	23.0	410.5	7.29	0.563
	S.S.	314	24.9	242,900	6.83	356
Tiffin **	O.P.	144	37.1	65.0	6.38	0.102
	T.P.	203	62.6	731.2	13.3	0.550
	S.S.	132	58.3	263,500	9.00	292.5

* Metric-English conversions: 1 cubic meter/second = 35.3 cubic feet/second;
1 metric ton = 1.102 short tons.

** The Tiffin gage station is located at Tindall Bridge just south of Fremont.

The data base used to calculate weighted mean concentrations at each stream gage station is summarized in Table 2. In addition to the number of individual samples, the observed total loading and the observed total flow, the mean flow during the sampling period is shown. This value was obtained by dividing the total observed flow by the total time over which the total loading and total flow were calculated. Comparison of the mean flow during the sampling period with the mean flow for the period of record allows evaluation of sampling bias.

The mean annual transport of materials at each stream gage was obtained by multiplying the mean annual flow by the weighted mean concentrations. These calculations are shown in Table 3. The values of the mean annual flow are based on the entire period of hydrological record at each station and were obtained from *Water Quality Records for Ohio, Part I* (U.S. Department of Interior, 1974).

Table 4 shows the calculations of non-point source yields of total phosphorus for each subbasin, using the model previously described. Point source inputs of total phosphorus within each subbasin were obtained by using a population equivalent of 2.1 kg/person/yr and the populations served by sewer collection systems within each subbasin. The value, 2.1 kg/person/yr, was obtained from studies of the effluents from the sewage treatment plants of the two largest cities (Tiffin and Bucyrus) and a detailed study of combined sewer overflows in Bucyrus (Burgess and Niple Ltd., 1969; Baker and Kramer, 1973.)

The yields of suspended solids for each subbasin are shown in Table 5. For suspended solids, point source inputs are disregarded. Since soluble orthophosphate is rapidly converted into the organic and/or bound forms,

Table 3: Calculation of Mean Annual Transport of Ortho Phosphorus, Total Phosphorus and Suspended Solids at U.S. Geological Survey Stream Gages in the Sandusky River Basin

Station	Parameter	Weighted Mean Concentration mg/l	Mean Annual Flow m ³ /s	Mean Annual Transport metric tons
Tymochtee	O.P.	0.071	5.098	11.4
	T.P.	0.499		80.1
	S.S.	271		43,570.
Bucyrus	O.P.	0.230	2.353	17.1
	T.P.	0.563		41.8
	S.S.	173		12,860.
Upper Sandusky	O.P.	0.139	6.768	29.7
	T.P.	0.580		123.8
	S.S.	294		62,690.
Mexico	O.P.	0.098	16.14	49.9
	T.P.	0.563		286.6
	S.S.	356		181,000.
Tiffin *	O.P.	0.102	26.65	85.7
	T.P.	0.550		462.2
	S.S.	292.5		245,800.

* The "Tiffin" Gage Station is at Tindall Bridge just south of Fremont.

Table 4: Calculation of Non-point Source Yields of Total Phosphorus for Subbasins Within the Sandusky River Basin

Subbasin	Stream Output t/yr	Stream Input t/yr	Point Source Inputs* t/yr	Non-point Source Yield t/yr
Tymochtee	80.1	--	--	80.1
Bucyrus	41.8	--	40.2	1.6
Upper Sandusky	123.8	41.8	11.9	70.1
Mexico	286.6	203.9	7.4	75.3
Tiffin	462.2	286.6	49.3	126.3
Total for Basin	--	--	102.8	353.4
Source as Percent	--	--	23.5	76.5

* Based on 2.1 kg/person/yr (4.6 lbs/person/yr) for sewered population in each subbasin.

Table 5: Calculation of Suspended Sediment Yields for Subbasins in the Sandusky River Basin

Subbasin	Stream Output 10 ³ metric tons	Stream Input 10 ³ metric tons	Subbasin Yield 10 ³ metric tons
Tymochtee	43.37	--	43.57
Bucyrus	12.86	--	12.86
Upper Sandusky	62.69	12.86	49.83
Mexico	181.0	106.26	74.74
Tiffin	245.8	181.0	64.80

the assumption of a 100% delivery ratio from upstream and point source inputs could not be made. Consequently, subbasin yields for soluble orthophosphate have not been calculated.

In order to compare the total phosphorus and suspended sediment transport at the stream gages and the non-point source yields from the subbasins, the results are presented as runoff coefficients in Table 6. For the gage stations, the mean annual transport at each station has been divided by the total drainage area upstream from that station. For the subbasins, the non-point source yields of phosphorus and suspended sediments from each subbasin were divided by the area of that subbasin. For both the stream gage stations and the subbasins, the ratios of phosphorus yield (in kg) to suspended sediments (in tons) are also shown.

DISCUSSION

The method of calculating non-point source yields of phosphorus and sediments used in this study depends on accurate estimates of the mean annual transport at stream gages. Weighted mean concentrations can provide such estimates only when the data used in the calculation of the weighted mean are proportionally representative of the long-term transport characteristics of the stream. Since the bulk of material transport occurs during periods of high flow, it is especially critical that the data include many measurements at high flow conditions. Comparison of the mean flow during the sampling period (table 2) with the mean annual flow for the period of record (table 3) indicates that our sampling was, in fact, biased toward high flow conditions. To avoid such flow bias would require many additional samples at low flows.

Table 6: Runoff Coefficients for Total Phosphorus and Suspended Sediments at Stream Gages and for Subbasins *

Stream Gage or Subbasin	T.P. kg/ha/yr	Stream Gages S.S. tons/ha/yr	Ratio kg P/ton SS	T.P. n-p** kg/ha/yr	Subbasins S.S. tons/ha/yr	Ratio kg P/ton SS
Tymochtee	1.35	.73	1.84	1.35	.73	1.84
Bucyrus	1.82	.56	3.25	.07	.56	.125
Upper Sandusky	1.60	.81	1.97	1.29	.92	1.40
Mexico	1.43	.90	1.51	1.18	1.17	1.01
Tiffin	1.43	.76	1.88	1.02	.52	1.96

* Metric-English conversions: 1 kilgram/hectare/year = 0.89 pounds/acre/year;
1 metric ton/hectare/year = 0.45 short tons/acre/year.

** Non-point source phosphorus only.

These samples would have little effect on either the total observed load or the total observed flow, and consequently would have little effect on the weighted mean concentration. Other more complex methods of using these data to estimate mean annual transport have been examined and yield similar results.

These studies confirm earlier findings of the dominance of non-point sources of phosphorus in the loading from the Sandusky River Basin into Lake Erie. Furthermore, the calculated non-point source phosphorus yields are large in all but one of the subbasins in the Sandusky Basin. For all of the subbasins except Bucyrus, the calculated minimum non-point source yields exceeded 1 kg/ha/yr. A survey of previous studies of nutrient transport from agricultural watersheds conducted for the International Reference Group on Great Lakes Pollution from Land Use Activities found an average yield of 0.38 kg/ha/yr (International Joint Commission, 1974, Part A6). A summary of another literature survey showed average and maximum runoff coefficients of 0.3 and 1.0 kg/ha/yr respectively from agricultural land (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1974). As noted by Ryden et al (1973), there is a great need for detailed long-term studies of phosphorus yields from streams draining agricultural watersheds. There are relatively few studies available that allow direct comparison between the non-point source phosphorus yields for the Sandusky subbasins and yields from other areas of comparable size and land use.

In comparison to other river basins in Northwestern Ohio, the Sandusky is not unique in its high phosphorus yields. During January through May 1975, measurements of nutrient and sediment yields at the stream gages nearest Lake Erie in the Maumee, Portage, Sandusky and Huron River Basins gave runoff

coefficients for total phosphorus of 1.59, 1.25, 1.29 and 1.05 kg/ha/yr respectively (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 1975). The methods used in that study were the same as described here, although the yields listed above include both point and non-point sources of phosphorus. It should be noted that at least some point source control efforts were in operation in each river basin during the above study.

It is noteworthy that the Tymochtee subbasin had the highest non-point source phosphorus runoff coefficient. This subbasin contains no municipal point sources and the rural population density is lower than that of any other subbasin. Given the low population density, septic tank runoff could not account for much of the non-point source phosphorus yield, even if the delivery ratio of phosphorus from septic tanks to streams was high. The possibility that feedlot runoff is contributing significantly to the phosphorus yield from this subbasin has not been directly investigated. If feedlot runoff acts like a point source, giving rise to increasing phosphorus concentrations as the stream flow decreases, this source would be insignificant because the phosphorus concentrations are lowest at low flows. The very close correlation between sediment and total phosphorus concentrations (figure 3) suggests surface runoff as the major source of the phosphorus. Part of the runoff could come from feedlots.

The unrealistically low non-point source runoff coefficient of total phosphorus from the Bucyrus subbasin has several possible explanations. Underestimation of total transport at the Bucyrus output station, overestimation of point source inputs within the subbasin and/or less than 100% delivery of total phosphorus from point source inputs through the subbasin could account for the low value. The extremely low phosphorus/sediment ratio for the Bucyrus subbasin (table 6) also indicates that the non-point source yield of phosphorus for this subbasin is being underestimated.

The data for the Bucyrus gage are based on daily grab samples. As the smallest subbasin in area, runoff events would have the shortest duration. Since an automatic sampler was not used at this station, it is possible that peak concentrations and peak flows have been missed.

Since the stream gage at Bucyrus is only 1 km downstream from the treatment plant effluent, a point source delivery ratio significantly less than 100% could only be occurring from phosphorus originating at the Crestline sewage treatment plant, which is located about 35 km upstream from the Bucyrus stream gage. It is well known that phosphorus originating from point sources can at least temporarily move onto the stream bottom (Keup, 1968). The magnitude of this instream phosphorus deposition for the Sandusky River is illustrated in a separate paper in this symposium (Baker and Kramer, 1975). If these phosphorus losses become permanent, then the delivery ratio from point sources of phosphorus could drop well below 100%.

Delivery ratios less than 100% in the other three subbasins containing point sources could explain the lower phosphorus runoff coefficients calculated for those subbasins than for the Tymochtee subbasin (table 6). If the delivery ratio from inland point sources to Lake Erie is significantly less than 100%, the effectiveness of phosphorus removal at inland treatment plants in reducing loading into the lake will be less than for comparable removal at point sources emptying directly into the lake.

The question of the delivery ratio of phosphorus from inland point sources to Lake Erie is closely related to the question of the delivery ratio of sediments through subbasins along the Sandusky. In calculating subbasin yields for suspended sediments (table 5), we assumed that all of the sediment entering

a subbasin from upstream sources was part of the output from the subbasin. Neither deposition behind low-head dams on the stream nor deposition on flood plains was assumed to be significant. If phosphorus from point sources becomes associated with sediment, either while temporarily on the stream bottom or while in transit during runoff events, then the subsequent delivery of that phosphorus to Lake Erie will depend on the delivery of the sediments to the Lake. In other words, a 100% delivery of phosphorus from point sources may depend on a 100% delivery of sediment through the stream. Literature dealing with the adsorption of soluble orthophosphate onto sediment particles has recently been reviewed by Ryden, et al (1973).

In most river basins the delivery ratio of sediments decreases as the area of the basin increases (Gottschalk, 1964; Great Lakes Basin Commission, 1975). This is generally reflected as a decrease in sediment runoff coefficients with increasing areas of drainage basins. This trend is not apparent in the Sandusky, at least as far as the Mexico stream gage, since the sediment runoff coefficients at stream gages increase from Bucyrus to Mexico (table 6). Previous estimates of sediment yields for Northwestern Ohio streams, based on calculated gross erosion rates and sediment delivery ratios obtained by extrapolation from studies of other river basins, resulted in significant underestimations of the observed sediment yields (Great Lakes Basin Commission, 1975). The discrepancy for the Maumee Basin (480,000 short tons/yr estimated versus 1,179,000 short tons/yr observed) was attributed to the delivery ratio component of the estimates. Possibly, the streams of Northwestern Ohio have unusually high delivery ratios of sediments. It should also be noted that according to estimates by the Pollution from Land Use Activities Reference Group, the river

basins of Northwestern Ohio contribute 39% of the total agriculturally derived sediment yield delivered from the United States to the Great Lakes (International Joint Commission, 1974).

One serious deficiency in the concept of delivery ratios, as normally conceived, is that it neglects particle sizes. Obviously, the delivery ratio for smaller particles is greater than for larger particles, everything else being equal. Yet the small particles, i.e. clays, bear the bulk of the exchange and binding sites for phosphorus or other potential pollutants. Consequently, the delivery ratio for non-point source phosphorus could be higher than for sediments. Furthermore, areas with higher gross erosion rates likely have larger average particle sizes and lower average delivery ratios to Lake Erie than areas with lower rates of gross erosion. The implications of this, relative to achieving significant reductions in the yields of sediments and non-point source phosphorus to Lake Erie, may be very significant. Sediment yields may not decrease in proportion to the reduction in gross erosion rates because of differences in delivery ratios from areas of high and low gross erosion rates.

As noted earlier, particle size analyses of sediments at the stream gages in the Sandusky Basin by the U.S. Geological Survey indicate the dominance of clay-sized particles even at the stations with the smallest drainage areas. This provides further justification for the assumption of 100% delivery of upstream sediments through the subbasins. Given this assumption, the resulting subbasin yields of suspended sediments, as calculated in Table 5 and expressed in Table 6, do show a general relationship to subbasin landscape characteristics. The Mexico subbasin, with a sediment yield of 1.17 t/ha/yr, includes a large

part of the terminal moraine which transects the Sandusky Basin in that area. With its relatively greater verticle relief, higher gross erosion rates and larger average particle sizes of the sediments from this subbasin may be expected. The phosphorus-to-sediment ratio is lower in the Mexico subbasin than in the others, with the exception of Bucyrus. In contrast, the Tiffin subbasin, which has the lowest unit area sediment yield, includes a large portion of flat lake-plain soils. The sediment derived from this area does, however, have the highest non-point source phosphorus-to-sediment ratio. This could be explained by the finer particle size associated with sediments derived from these intensively cultivated lake-plain soils. The low unit-area sediment yield from the Bucyrus subbasin could be associated, either directly or indirectly, with the fact that the subbasin also has the highest rural population density. The Upper Sandusky and Tymochtee subbasins are intermediate to those described above. More detailed correlation of subbasin yields with land capability and land-use characteristics will be undertaken upon completion of the comprehensive soil surveys currently in progress.

Given the magnitude of the non-point source yields of phosphorus from the Sandusky Basin (and other Northwestern Ohio streams), questions of the chemical forms and biological availability of the phosphorus associated with suspended sediments derived from sheet erosion become very important. The status of these questions has recently been reviewed (Ryden et al, 1973) and additional study is scheduled as part of Task D, of the Pollution from Land Use Activities Reference Group, International Joint Commission. The behavior of sediment-bound phosphorus in newly constructed upground reservoirs in Northwestern Ohio is also currently under investigation (Kramer and Baker, 1975).

CONCLUSIONS

The data indicate that non-point source phosphorus loading is more uniformly distributed over the landscape than is sediment loading. Excluding the Bucyrus subbasin, the phosphorus runoff coefficients ranged from 1.02 to 1.35 kg/ha/yr. Sediment yields ranged from 0.52 to 1.17 tons/ha/yr. We propose that differences in delivery ratios between the fine clays that bind phosphorus and the sediment fraction as a whole (clays and larger particles) can account for this observation. If correct, a consequence would be that non-point source phosphorus-control efforts need to be evaluated independently of erosion-control efforts, since the latter are primarily directed at areas of critical erosion problems. Controlling non-point phosphorus yields may prove even more difficult than controlling sediment yields in Northwestern Ohio.

The assumptions concerning delivery ratios of phosphorus and sediments, upon which is based the model for calculating non-point source yields from subbasins, are discussed in some detail. A better understanding of delivery ratios from streams in Northwestern Ohio will be essential for planning effective and efficient control measures for phosphorus originating from land-use activities. The magnitude of the phosphorus loading from non-point sources also underscores the need for evaluating the biological activity of phosphorus adsorbed to sediments originating from surface runoff.

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